

ISSN (p): 3030-3362

№ 6 (28)

27.06.2025

IF 2024
11.7

R

TADQIQ VA TATBIQ

Research and implementation

scientific-methodical journal

S C I E N C E S

Exact, Natural, Political, Social, Economic, Technical, Medical, Pedagogical

INTERNATIONAL
STANDARD
SERIAL
NUMBER
INTERNATIONAL CENTRE

CERTIFICATE
№ 078777

ral-journal.uz

@ferteach_uz

Editor in Chief:

F.M.Mukhtarov
PhD, associate prof

Executive editor

S.I.Zokirov
PhD, associate prof

Languages:

Uzbek, Russian, English and
Karakalpak

Registered in the Agency of
Information and Mass
Communications under the
Administration of the
President of the Republic of
Uzbekistan on May 3, 2023
under number 078777.

[IF-2024: 11.7](#)

[@ferteach_uz](#)

+99893-343-13-14

<https://rai-journal.uz>

Editorial Board:

B.R.Ismailov – Dr. Tech. Sc., Prof., M.Avezov South Kaz. Univ., Shymkent, Kazakhstan
I.Bjorn - Ph.D., Imeritus, Technical University of Denmark, Copenhagen, Denmark
A.Rasulov – Dr. Phys.-Math. Sc., Prof., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
L.K.Mamadaliyeva – Dr. Tech. Sc. (DSc), Prof., FerPI, Fergana, Uzbekistan
M.E.Yunusaliyev – Dr. Tech. Sc. (DSc), Prof., FerPI, Fergana, Uzbekistan
X.B.Ismailov – Can. Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., M.Avezov South Kaz. Univ., Shymkent, Kazakhstan
J.T.Moldaliyev – Can. Bio. Sc., Assoc. Prof., OshSU, Osh, Kyrgyzstan
O.S.Nazarmatov – DSc in Econ., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
G.K.Obidova - DSc in Ped., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
T.M.Abdullayev - Ph.D. in Tech. Sc., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan.
N.I.Ibrokhimov - Ph.D. in Phys.-Math., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan.
A.R.Nurmatov - Ph.D. in History, NamSU, Fergana, Uzbekistan.
T.Yu.Bakirov - PhD in Ped. Sc., FarSU, Fergana, Uzbekistan
D.F.Tukhtasinov - Ph.D. in Ped. Sc., TUIT Fergana branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan.
S.B.Atajonova - Ph.D in Ped. Sc., AndMI, Andijan Uzbekistan
Sh.A.Umarov - Ph.D. in Phys.-Math. Sc., TUIT Fergana branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan.
I.A.Rustamov - Ph.D. in Phil. Sc., TUIT Fergana branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan.
B.Kh.Tolipov - Ph.D. in Phil. Sc., TUIT Fergana branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan.
O.Kh.Otakulov - Can. Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., TUIT Fergana branch, Uzbekistan
O.S.Raimjonova - Ph.D in Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., TUIT Fergana branch, Uzbekistan
R.A.Nurdinova - Ph.D in Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., TUIT Fergana branch, Uzbekistan
M.I.Ismoilov - Ph.D in Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., TUIT Fergana branch, Uzbekistan
I.T.Tojiboyev - Can. Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., Fergana State University, Uzbekistan
Sh.J.Kholmatov - PhD., TUIT Fergana branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
Z.N.Khatamova - PhD. in Tech. Sc., TUIT Fergana branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
Q.Kh. Akhunov - Can. Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., Fergana Polytechnic Institute, Uzbekistan
M.Kh. Okhunov - Can. Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., Fergana Polytechnic Institute, Uzbekistan
A.Q. Khomidov - Can. Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., Fergana Polytechnic Institute, Uzbekistan
Sh.Sh. Akramov - PhD, TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
A.A. Salimov - PhD in Econ., Fergana Polytechnic Institute, Uzbekistan
Z.G'. Ubaydullayev – Can. Econ., TUIT Qarchi Branch, Qarchi, Uzbekistan
S.S. Ibragimov - Ph.D in Tech. Sc., AndMI, Andijan Uzbekistan
Sh.J. Kholmatov - Ph.D. in Phil., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
G.D. Kuchkarova - Ph.D. in Phil., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
I.R.Teshabayeva - Ph.D. in Tech. Sc., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
A.L.Meliquziyev - Ph.D. in Phil. Sc., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
O.U.Kholmatova - Ph.D. in Phil. Sc., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
N.N.Radjabov - Ph.D. in Phil. Sc., Assoc. Prof., Oriental University, Tashkent, Uzbekistan
Sh.A.Yuldashov - Ph.D. in Tech. Sc., Fergana State University, Fergana, Uzbekistan
A.A.Yuldashev - Ph.D. in Tech. Sc., Fergana State University, Fergana, Uzbekistan
M.Israilov - Can. Tech. Sc., Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan Academy of Forces
N.S.Abdullaeva - PhD in Ped. Sc., NamDU, Namangan, Uzbekistan
A.G.Turgunboyeva - PhD in Ped. Sc., NamDPI, Namangan, Uzbekistan
M.A.Abdullaeva - Prof., NamDU, Namangan, Uzbekistan
I.O.Ergashev - PhD in Econ., Fiscal Institute, Tashkent, Uzbekistan
N.T.Mamatxanova - PhD in Ped. Sc., NamDPI, Namangan, Uzbekistan
U.Yu.Akhundzhanov - PhD in Tech. Sc., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
O.M.Ergashev - PhD in Tech. Sc., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
N.R.Khallieva - PhD in Econ., Bukhara MTI, Bukhara, Uzbekistan
F.K.Achilova – Can. Econ. Sc., TUIT Qarchi Branch, Qarchi, Uzbekistan
A.K.Samyayev - PhD in Geog., Sam. Reg. Ped. Skills Center, Samarkand, Uzbekistan
J.S.Abdullayev - Can. Phys.-Math. Sc., Assoc. Prof., TUIT Fergana branch, Uzbekistan
N.D.Botirova –PhD in Ped, TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan

Bosh muharrir:

F.M.Mukhtarov
PhD, dotsent

Ijrochi muharrir:

S.I.Zokirov
PhD, dotsent

Nashr tillari:

O'zbek, Rus, Inzliz va
Qoraqalpoq

O'zbekiston Respublikasi
Prezidenti Administratsiyasi
huzuridagi Axborot va
ommaviy
kommunikatsiyalar agentligi
tomonidan 2023-yil
3-mayda 078777 raqami
bilan ro'yxatga olingan.

[IF-2024: 11.7](#)

[@ferteach_uz](#)

+99893-343-13-14

<https://rai-journal.uz>

Tahrir hay'ati:

B.R.Ismailov – t.f.d., prof. M.Avezov Jan. Qoz. Univ-ti., Chimkent, Qozog'iston
I.Byorno – Ph.D., Imeritus, Daniya Texnika Universiteti, Kopengagen, Daniya
A.Rasulov – f.-m.f.d., prof.TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
L.K.Mamadaliyeva – t.f.d. (DSc), prof. FarPI, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
M.E.Yunusaliyev – t.f.d. (DSc), prof. FarPI, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
X.B.Ismailov – t.f.n., dot., M.Avezov Jan. Qoz. Univ-ti., Chimkent, Qozog'iston
J.T.Moldaliyev – bio. f. n., dotsent. OshDU, Osh, Qirg'iziston
O.S.Nazarmatov – iqt.f.d. DSc, TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
G.K.Obidova – ped.f.d. DSc, TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
T.M.Abdullayev – t.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.
N.I.Ibrokhimov – f.-m.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.
A.R.Nurmatov – tarix f.b. Ph.D., NamDU, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.
T.Yu.Bakirov – ped. f.b. PhD, FarDU, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
D.F.To'xtasinov – ped.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.
S.B.Atajonova – ped.f.b. Ph.D, AndMI, Andijon O'zbekiston
Sh.A.Umarov – f.-m.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.
I.A.Rustamov – fal.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.
B.X.Tolipov – f.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.
O.X.Otaqulov – t.f.n., dotsent. TATU Farg'ona filiali, O'zbekiston
O.S.Raimjonova – t.f.b. Ph.D, dotsent, TATU Farg'ona filiali, O'zbekiston
R.A.Nurdinova – t.f.b. Ph.D, dotsent, TATU Farg'ona filiali, O'zbekiston
M.I.Ismoilov – t.f.b. Ph.D, dotsent, TATU Farg'ona filiali, O'zbekiston
I.T.Tojiboyev – t.f.n., dotsent, Farg'ona davlat universiteti, O'zbekiston
Sh.J.Kholmatov – i.i.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
Z.N.Khatamova – t.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
Q.X. Axunov – t.f.n., dotsent, Farg'ona politexnika instituti, O'zbekiston
M.X. Oxunov – t.f.n., dotsent, Farg'ona politexnika instituti, O'zbekiston
A.Q.Xomidov – t.f.n., dotsent, Farg'ona politexnika instituti, O'zbekiston
Sh.Sh.Akramov – q.x.f.b. PhD, TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
A.A.Salimov – iqt.f.b. PhD, Farg'ona politexnika instituti, O'zbekiston
Z.G'.Ubaydullayev – iqt.f.n., TATU Qarchi filiali, Qarchi, O'zbekiston
S.S.Ibragimov – t.f.b. Ph.D, AndMI, Andijon O'zbekiston
Sh.J.Xolmatov – fal.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
G.D.Kuchkarova – fal.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
I.R.Teshabayeva – t.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
A.L.Meliqiziyev – fil.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
O.U.Xolmatova – fil.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
N.N.Radjabov – fil.f.b. Ph.D., dotsent, Oriental University, Toshkent, O'zbekiston
Sh.A.Yuldashov – t.f.b. Ph.D., Farg'ona davlat universiteti, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
A.A.Yuldashev – t.f.b. Ph.D., Farg'ona davlat universiteti, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
M.Israilov – t.f.n., O'zbekiston Respublikasi Qurolli Kuchlar Akademiyasi
N.S.Abdullayeva – p.f.b. PhD, NamDU, Namangan, O'zbekiston
A.G.Turg'unboyeva – p.f.b. PhD, NamDPI, Namangan, O'zbekiston
M.A.Abdullayeva – professor, NamDU, Namangan, O'zbekiston
I.O.Ergashev – iqt.f.b. PhD, Fiskal instituti, Toshkent, O'zbekiston
N.T.Mamatxanova – p.f.b. PhD, NamDPI, Namangan, O'zbekiston
U.Yu.Axundjanov – t.f.b. PhD, TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
O.M.Ergashev – t.f.b. PhD, TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
N.R.Xallieva – iqt.f.b. PhD, Buxoro MTI, Buxoro, O'zbekiston
F.K.Achilova – iqt.f.n., TATU Qarchi filiali, Qarchi, O'zbekiston
A.K.Samyayev – g.f.b. PhD, Sam. vil. ped. mah. mar, Samarqand, O'zbekiston
J.S.Abdullayev – f.-m.f.n., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.
N.D.Botirova – ped.f.b. PhD, TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston

AI-driven cybersecurity: opportunities, challenges, and threats

Mirzayev Muhammadjon Muhammadayub ugli¹, Asatullayev Diyorbek Mirzatillo ugli²

¹Fergana State Technical University

e-mail: 97muhammadjon97@gmail.com ,

²Fergana State Technical University, Student

e-mail: asatullayevdiyorbek3@gmail.com

Copyright: © 2025 by the author.

Licensee: This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Abstract: The cyberattack surface in modern enterprise environments is massive, and it's continuing to grow rapidly. This means that analyzing and improving an organization's cybersecurity posture needs more than mere human intervention.

Keywords: cybersecurity, cyberattack, AI(artificial intelligence), Detecting New Threats, Battling Bots, Breach Risk Prediction.

Кибербезопасность на основе ИИ: возможности, проблемы и угрозы

Мирзаев Мухаммаджон Мухаммадаюб угли¹, Асатуллаев Диёрбек Мирзатилло угли²

¹Ферганский государственный технический университет

e-mail: 97muhammadjon97@gmail.com ,

²Ферганский государственный технический университет, студент

e-mail: asatullayevdiyorbek3@gmail.com

Аннотация: Поверхность кибератак в современных корпоративных средах огромна и продолжает быстро расти. Это означает, что для анализа и улучшения состояния кибербезопасности организации требуется нечто большее, чем просто человеческое вмешательство.

Ключевые слова: кибербезопасность, кибератака, ИИ (искусственный интеллект), обнаружение новых угроз, борьба с ботами, прогнозирование риска нарушений.

Alga asoslangan kiberxavfsizlik: imkoniyatlar, muammolar va tahdidlar

Mirzayev Muhammadjon Muhammadayub ugli¹, Asatullayev Diyorbek Mirzatillo ugli²

¹Farg‘ona davlat texnika universiteti

e-mail: 97muhammadjon97@gmail.com ,

²Farg‘ona davlat texnika universiteti, talaba

e-mail: asatullayevdiyorbek3@gmail.com

Annотatsiya. Zamonaviy korporativ muhitda kiberhujum maydoni juda katta va u tez sur'atlar bilan o'sishda davom etmoqda. Bu shuni anglatadiki, tashkilotning kiberxavfsizlik holatini tahlil qilish va yaxshilash inson aralashuvidan ko'ra ko'proq narsani talab qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: kiberxavfsizlik, kiberhujum, AI (sun'iy intellekt), yangi tahdidlarni aniqlash, botlarga qarshi kurash, buzilish xavfini bashorat qilish.

Introduction

Cyber security has become a major concern in the digital era. Data breaches, ID theft, cracking the captcha, and other such stories abound, affecting millions of individuals as well as organizations. The challenges have always been endless in inventing right controls and procedures and implementing them with acute perfection for tackling with cyber-attacks and crimes. The ever-increasing risk of cyber-attacks and crimes grew exponentially with recent advancements in artificial intelligence. It has been applied in almost every field of sciences and engineering. From healthcare to robotics, AI has created a revolution. This ball of fire couldn't be kept away from cyber criminals, and thus, the “usual” cyber-attacks have now become “intelligent” cyber-attacks. Furthermore, poor cybersecurity in the protection of open-source models may lead to hacking opportunities for actors seeking to steal such information. Limitations to the dissemination and the sharing of data and codes could enable a more complete assessment of the security risks related to the technology and its vulgarisation.

Methods :To understand the role of AI in cybersecurity, a qualitative review was conducted on existing applications of AI technologies such as machine learning (ML), natural language processing (NLP), and pattern recognition within cybersecurity frameworks. Sources included academic articles, cybersecurity reports, and case studies on AI-based threat detection, bot management, and adversarial AI. The study also considered public cases and scenarios where AI was misused by attackers, such as bypassing facial recognition systems.

Artificial intelligence- AI presents many advantages and applications in a variety of areas, cybersecurity being one of them. With fast-evolving cyberattacks and rapid multiplication of devices happening today, AI and machine learning can help to keep abreast with cybercriminals, automate threat detection, and respond more effectively than conventional software-driven or manual techniques. Here are a few advantages and applications of using AI in cybersecurity:

Detecting New Threats: AI can be used to spot cyber threats and possibly malicious activities. Traditional software systems simply cannot keep pace with the sheer number of new malwares created every week, so this is an area AI can really help with. By using sophisticated algorithms, AI systems are being trained to detect malware, run pattern recognition, and detect even the minutest behaviors of malware or ransomware attacks before it enters the system. AI allows for superior predictive intelligence with natural language processing which curates data on its own by scraping through articles, news, and studies on cyber threats. This can give intelligence of new anomalies, cyberattacks, and prevention strategies. After all, cybercriminals follow trends too so what's popular with them changes constantly.

AI-based cybersecurity systems can provide the latest knowledge of global as well as industry-specific dangers to better formulate vital prioritization decisions based not merely on what could be used to attack your systems but based on what is most likely to be used to attack your systems.

Battling Bots: Bots make up a huge chunk of internet traffic today, and they can be dangerous. From account takeovers with stolen credentials to bogus account creation and data fraud, bots can be a real menace. You can't tackle automated threats with manual responses alone. AI and machine learning help build a thorough understanding of website traffic and distinguish between good bots (like search engine crawlers), bad bots, and humans. AI enables us to analyze a vast amount of data and allows cybersecurity teams to adapt their strategy to a continually altering landscape.

Downsides of AI in Cybersecurity: The advantages discussed above are just a small chunk of the potential of AI in improving cybersecurity. However, as with anything, there are also some downsides to using AI in this field. In order to build and maintain an AI system, organizations would need substantially more resources and financial investments. Furthermore, as AI systems are trained using data sets, you must acquire many distinct sets of malware codes, non-malicious codes, and anomalies. Acquiring all of these data sets is time-intensive and requires investments that most organizations cannot afford. Without huge volumes of data and events, AI systems can

render incorrect results and/or false positives. And getting inaccurate data from unreliable sources can even backfire.

Use of AI by Adversaries: AI can be used by cybersecurity professionals to reinforce cybersecurity best practices and minimize the attack surface rather than continually being on the lookout for malicious activity. On the flipside, cybercriminals can take advantage of those same AI systems for malicious purposes. Adversarial AI “causes machine learning models to misinterpret inputs into the system and behave in a way that’s favorable to the attacker,” according to Accenture.

For example, an iPhone’s “FaceID” access feature uses neural networks to recognize faces, making it susceptible to adversarial AI attacks. Hackers could construct adversarial images to bypass the Face ID security features and easily continue their attack without drawing attention.

Results

The analysis revealed that AI significantly improves cybersecurity outcomes in several key areas:

- **Threat Detection:** AI identifies new malware and unusual user behavior using pattern recognition and predictive modeling.
- **Automated Response:** NLP enables AI systems to extract cyber threat intelligence from global sources in real-time.
- **Bot Mitigation:** AI distinguishes between good bots, malicious bots, and humans in web traffic, reducing data fraud and fake account creation.
- **Risk Prioritization:** AI systems assist in prioritizing vulnerabilities based on active threats rather than general weakness lists.

Nevertheless, the use of AI is constrained by:

- **High Costs:** AI systems demand substantial financial and technical resources.
- **Data Dependency:** Accuracy depends on large volumes of quality data.
- **Adversarial Risks:** Attackers can manipulate AI systems to bypass security (e.g., adversarial images in facial recognition).

Discussion

While AI offers considerable promise in enhancing cybersecurity, its implementation is not without risk. Cybercriminals can utilize AI for creating more adaptive and evasive threats. The concept of adversarial AI — where attackers manipulate inputs to deceive AI models — is especially concerning. This highlights

the need for robust AI governance, ethical standards, and continuous model monitoring. Organizations must weigh the costs and challenges against the benefits when adopting AI-driven cybersecurity measures. Strategic implementation, continuous learning, and collaboration with AI security experts are vital for maximizing benefits while minimizing risks.

References:

1. Yudkowsky, E. Artificial intelligence as a positive and negative factor in global risk. Oxford city. Oxford University Press 2008-y.303.
2. Vidhya P.M. (February 2014). CYBER SECURITY. International Journal of Computer Science and Mobile Computing. 3 (2), 586–590.
3. ERGASHEV O.M. ENSURING INFORMATION SECURITY OF RADIO ENGINEERING SYSTEMS // Theory and practice of modern science. – 2018. – №. 6. – С. 689-691.
4. Daniel R. Faust.” Cybersecurity Expert”.New York. PowerKids Press 2018-y.582 pg.
5. Yudkowsky, E. 2008. Artificial intelligence as a positive and negative factor in global risk. In
6. Global catastrophic risks. Oxford University Press. 303.

Jurnal haqida

“Tadqiq va tatbiq” ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali Fer-Teach MChJ tomonidan tashkil etilgan. Mazkur jurnal O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan 2023 yil 3 mayda №078777 raqam bilan ro‘yxatga olingan.

ISSN 3030-3362

Jurnalda texnologiya sohasidagi ixtisoslashtirilgan jurnal bo‘lib, texnik fanlarning turli sohalari: fizika, matematika, axborot texnologiyalari bo‘yicha tadqiqot va ishlanmalarning barcha asosiy yo‘nalishlarini qamrab oladi. Jurnalda tilshunoslik, o‘qitish metodikasi va texnika fanlarining rivojlanish tarixiga oid ilmiy maqolalar ham chop etiladi.

Manzil: 15010, Farg‘ona viloyati, Farg‘ona shahri, ko‘ch. Solima, 23/4, kvartira. 26

E-mail: chief_editor@rai-journal.uz

Web-sayt: <https://rai-journal.uz/>

Tillar: o‘zbek, rus, ingliz, qoraqalpoq

О журнале

Научно-методический журнал «Исследования и внедрение» учрежден ООО «FerTeach». Данный журнал зарегистрирован номером № 078777 Агентством информации и массовых коммуникаций при Администрации Президента Республики Узбекистан от 3 мая 2023 года.

ISSN 3030-3362

«Исследования и внедрение» является специализированным журналом в области технологий и охватывает все основные направления исследований и разработок в различных областях технических наук: физика, математика, информационные технологии. Журнал также публикует научные статьи по языкознанию, методике преподавания и истории развития технических наук.

Адрес: 150100, Ферганская область, г. Фергана, ул. Солима, 23/4, кв. 26

E-mail: chief_editor@rai-journal.uz

Сайт: <https://rai-journal.uz/>

Языки: узбекский, русский, английский, каракалпакский

About the journal

The scientific and methodological journal "Research and Implementation" was founded by Fer-Teach LLC. This journal is registered under number 078777 by the Agency for Information and Mass Communications under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 3, 2023.

ISSN 3030-3362

"Research and Implementation" is a specialized journal in the field of technology and covers all the main areas of research and development in various fields of technical sciences: physics, mathematics, information technology. The journal also publishes scientific articles on linguistics, teaching methods and the history of the development of technical sciences.

Address: 150100, Fergana region, Fergana city, Solima street, 23/4, apt. 26

E-mail: chief_editor@rai-journal.uz

Website: <https://rai-journal.uz/>

Languages: Uzbek, Russian, English, Karakalpak

DIQQAT!

Jurnal materiallaridan foydalanganda manbani ko'rsatish kerak.

Maqola mualliflari maqolalar mazmuni va ularning nashr etilishi fakti uchun javobgardirlar.

Har doim ham mualliflarning fikrlari tahririyat nuqtai nazarini ifodalamaydi va nashr etilgan ma'lumotlarning haqiqiyliги uchun javobgar emas.

Jurnal tahririyati mualliflar va/yoki uchinchi shaxslar va tashkilotlarga maqolaning e'lon qilinishi natijasida yetkazilishi mumkin bo'lgan zarar uchun javobgar emas.

ВНИМАНИЕ!

При использовании материалов журнала необходимо указывать источник. Авторы статей несут ответственность за содержание статей и за сам факт их публикации.

Редакция не всегда разделяет мнения авторов и не несет ответственности за недостоверность публикуемых данных.

Редакция журнала не несет никакой ответственности перед авторами и/или третьими лицами и организациями за возможный ущерб, вызванный публикацией статьи.

ATTENTION!

When using journal materials, you must indicate the source.

The authors of the articles are responsible for the content of the articles and for the very fact of their publication.

The editors do not always share the opinions of the authors and are not responsible for the unreliability of the published data.

The editorial board of the journal does not bear any responsibility to the authors and / or third parties and organizations for possible damage caused by the publication of the article
